

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Creating 3D Models from Datasets

The technical 3D modeling procedure

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Introduction

This SOP covers the entire technical 3D modeling procedure: segmenting organs from datasets in Slicer, modifying them in ZBrush, aligning new organs with the already created VH bodies, using Maya to add “metadata”, and exporting the models with metadata. It also includes common tips for Maya and ZBrush for the 3D modeler to reference. It is intended for the 3D modeler as a breakdown of the technical steps but does not encapsulate the full communication or responsibilities of this process.

Roles and responsibilities

The **3D Modeler** builds 3D models, negotiates and implements suggested changes with the SME(s), and uploads the models for usage in HuBMAP services and user interfaces.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
3D Modeler	Heidi Schlehlein	hschleh@iu.edu

Procedures

Segment model from the [VH dataset](#) when possible. To do that, follow these steps:

- Download [3D Slicer 4.6.2](#) (best version for segmentation tools)
- Load (not DICOM option) data from computer
 - Load images and segmentation files (.nrrd file type)
 - Make sure single file is checked for both (show options)
 - Make sure Label Map is selected for segmentation files
 - Tip: Kristen Browne used every 3rd image for the VHF, which was 0.33mm slices. The male was 1 mm slices so every image was used.
- To begin segmentation, use the Editor tool.

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- Use Threshold Effect tool
 - Slide until desired section is mostly highlighted
 - Use for paint
- Turn on PaintEffect tool
 - This is a 3D tool--use Sphere mode
 - Smaller sphere sometimes processes faster
 - Sometimes faster (like for vessels) to go anterior to posterior through the body to do more at once
 - Erase with EraseLabel tool
- When ready, hit MakeModelEffect tool
 - Hit apply
 - If taking too long, can go to ModelMaker and increase decimation to make resolution lower
 - Can also do a bunch of models at once by hitting start range to end range
- Save as stl
 - Try to export all from same session- otherwise it may not line up
- Take into ZBrush, dynamesh it
- To clean up use ChangelandEffect
 - Choose another color
 - Select model you want to keep
 - ModelMaker-Apply
- See video saved here of Kristen's steps:
https://drive.google.com/file/d/1yU92nSRResTvkwXSC_ITMseIP1QuBYYfp/view?usp=sharing

To import GLB model into ZBrush from Maya:

- Open model in Maya and use GoZ plugin to open in ZBrush
 - **-or-**
- Open file in Blender. File-Import-Import glb
- Select parts you want to export
- Export at stl File-Export-Export stl
 - In dialog box, hit "export selected" and "batch export" if want separate stl files
- In Zbrush, draw out an object and enter edit mode.
- Import by Zplugin-SubTool Master- MultiAppend (it often crashes)

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ZBrush sculpting tips:

- When you have sections and remesh it, it will separate the files. Use Geometry-crease to maintain hard angles
 - ZRemesher- keep creases to maintain boundary line, turn off smooth groups
 - Makes better geometry than Dynamesh, and good at making a smaller poly model
 - Use FreezeBorder
 - When Zremesher doesn't work, then decimate it- ZPlugin- Decimation master
 - Use this when needing a smaller model
- Dynamesh- turn project and/or blur off to maintain geometry
 - Used to redistribute polygons when they have been stretched or pinched
 - Used to do quick booleans. Use IMM mesh brush to add or subtract shapes then dynamesh to add/sub to original shape.
- If need to merge subtools down, use weld so the final tool moves together when you make edits

To export from ZBrush to Maya:

- Can use GoZ but be aware it can glitch- can only do a certain # of subtools at a time

Maya sculpting tips:

- Freeze transformations to set scale to lower than 1cm
 - Shift+Click opens everything
 - Select all
 - Shift+H show all
 - Modify-center pivot to realign all center points
 - Modify-freeze transformations

Keep alignment when adding new models to United file (tips):

- Refer to original segmentation from VH database to align.
- Pull out segmentation of multiple organs as one file from Slicer into a Maya file.
- Import any surrounding organs already lined up into Zbrush.
- Use GoZ or FBX of just pieces interested in between Maya and Zbrush.
- Do alignment before start sculpting
 - Bring organs to United file, scale and align
 - Freeze transformations
 - Save as FBX
 - Bring to Zbrush and that's the starting file

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See video of Kristen describing the process here (4 min long):

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/14S6FPCSFTUG9nlotSoa2WwTK5FWXC3LI/view?usp=sharing>

Maya metadata export (Node list export for Ontology Crosswalk Table Compilation):

- First- Freeze Transformations of all models (Select all models, Modify- Freeze transformations)
- Find MEL code here:
<https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-3d-reference-object-library/tree/master/MetadataScript>
 - To add delAttr button:
 - Copy code from “delete_all_attributes_on_selected” and add as Python code
 - Drag up to shelf and create a button
 - To add PrintAttr button:
 - Copy code from “OutputAttributes” and add as MEL code
 - Drag up to shelf and create a button
- Select All.
- First step is to delete all existing attributes.
 - Hit the delAttr button.
- Then new attributes need to be added.
 - Modify- Add Attribute (keep selecting all)
 - Select “String” in Data Type area
 - Add the 6 headers of the columns on the Ontology Crosswalk Table Compilation spreadsheet
 - In “Long name” field, add “anatomical_structure_of”, hit “add”
 - In “Long name” field, add “source_spatial_entity”, hit “add”
 - SKIP “NODE NAME”
 - In “Long name” field, add “label”, hit “add”
 - In “Long name” field, add “ontologyid”, hit “add”
 - In “Long name” field, add “representation_of”, hit “add”
 - In “Long name” field, add “glb_file_of_single_organs”, hit “add”
- Delete top rows of Ontology Crosswalk Table Compilation spreadsheet, and save as new spreadsheet (NodeList_Date) with two tabs: one named source, one named input.
 - All blank cells needs a hyphen
 - Select whole data range
 - Go to Find and Select- Go to Special- select Blanks- hit ok
 - It will highlight all the blank cells- add a dash- ctrl+enter to go to fill all cells
- Separate out Male and Female information (there will be four tabs in total: InputM, InputF, SourceF, SourceM).
- Save the workbook in a consistent place.

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- Folder with date
 - VHM and VHF folders
 - Name workbook "NodeList_Date"
- Save Input tab as a csv (comma delineated) file.
- ***at min 47 in video, Kristen has a description of what the lines of code in the MEL script all do***
- Copy setExtraAttributes into Mel code portion of script editor.
- Hit execute (play button).
- Select all models.
- Type into script editor
"getAttributes("D:/HuBMAP/NodeLists/11182021/VH_M/import.csv")" and replace directory with where import file is saved.
- *NOTE THAT SLASHES ARE REVERSED IN MEL SCRIPT (if copy and paste path from windows, will need to reverse backslashes).*
 - Have to close excel file before running code
- Clear history and hit play.
- Once all the attributes have been added, select everything.
- Run the OutputAttributes script.
 - Copy it all (in history view)
 - Paste into original spreadsheet (not input, only csv)
 - Data- Text to Columns
 - Hit Next-change to comma, hit Finish
- Delete extra rows:
 - Select node list column
 - Data-Filter-Select blank
 - Select all the rows where the numbers are skipped, all the way down to where the numbers go in order again- delete these rows
 - Bottom row of data should be flush- each column has data
- Save excel sheet as Node List with date.
- Save maya file as a maya binary file (FBX will also save all the attributes).
- Excel sheet should have 6 sheets- SourceM, SourceF, ImportM, ImportF, ExportM, ExportF- name sheet nodelist with date (NodeList_Date).
- Upload to GitHub.

Maya Metadata export for landmark/extraction sites:

- First- Freeze Transformations of all models (Select all models, Modify- Freeze transformations).
- Select All.
- First step is to delete all existing attributes.
 - Hit the delAttr button.
- Then new attributes need to be added.

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- Modify- Add Attribute (keep selecting all)
- Select “String” in Data Type area
- Add the 5 headers of the columns on the Ontology Crosswalk Table Compilation spreadsheet
 - In “Long name” field, add “extraction_set_for”, hit “add”
 - In “Long name” field, add “extraction_set_id”, hit “add”
 - In “Long name” field, add “extraction_set_label”, hit “add”
 - In “Long name” field, add “source_spatial_entity”, hit “add”
 - SKIP “NODE NAME”
 - In “Long name” field, add “label”, hit “add”
- Copy setExtraAttributes_Extractions into Mel code portion of script editor.
- Hit execute (play button).
- Select all models.
- Type into script editor
“getAttributesExtractions(“D:/HuBMAP/NodeLists/11182021/VH_M/import.csv”)” and replace directory with where import file is saved.
- *NOTE THAT SLASHES ARE REVERSED IN MEL SCRIPT (if copy and paste path from windows, will need to reverse backslashes)*
 - Have to close excel file before running code
- Clear history and hit play.
- Once all the attributes have been added, select everything.
- Run the OutputAttributesExtractions script.
 - Copy it all (in history view)
 - Paste into original spreadsheet (not input, only csv)
 - Data- Text to Columns
 - Hit Next-change to comma, hit Finish
- Follow the rest of the instructions above for organ metadata.

Code troubleshooting:

// Error: line 29: setAttr: Not enough data was provided. The last 1036 items will be skipped. //

Usually means there are empty cells in the csv that need to be filled in with a dash

// Error: line 11: Cannot convert data of type string[] to type string. //

Means that you don't have the same node name in the excel as you do in the Maya

Maya Tips:

- To change a large number of node names in Maya, select all you want to change, go to Modify-search and replace- and make your changes

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- Install Babylon Maya plugin
 - doc.babylonjs.com/extensions/Exporters/Maya
 - When exporting with the plugin, change file type to GLB, check Export only selected
- Shading-XRay: use this to see through things
- Everything is a basic phong material in Maya right now- just change the color
 - May need to delete extra materials from babylon- Windows- Rendering editors-Hypershade-Edit-Delete unused nodes
- Keep colors the same across files- all the colors are saved in the United file

See video of Kristen describing process here:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1f_DVNx9xlvBPpxegw6RZ9yIzmxIY6Qj/view?usp=sharing

Export Tips:

- Use master united Maya file to make edits to models, then export from there as an FBX, because you will need to delete extra nodes. Then save as a GLB.

References

- ZBrush:
<https://pixologic.com/>
- Slicer:
<https://www.slicer.org/>
- Maya:
<https://www.autodesk.com/products/maya/overview?term=1-YEAR&tab=subscription>
- Blender:
<https://www.blender.org/>

Glossary

3D model: A 3D model is a digital object, consisting of vertices and edges, who, when taken together, can form a potentially endless variety of primitive (e.g., cubes, spheres, cones) and complex shapes (such as organs). 3D models come in many formats with various capabilities and limitations (OBJ, FBX, GLB, see below). We use GLB and FBX as output formats.

ASCT+B Tables: Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) Tables are authored by multiple experts across many consortia. Tables capture the partonomy of anatomical structures, cell types and major biomarkers (e.g., gene, protein, lipid or metabolic markers).

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GLB file format: Also called GL Transmission Format Binary file (.glb), this is a 3D file format specification, see <https://docs.fileformat.com/3d/glb/>.

GitHub: An online service for version control and code-sharing.

MEL script: Maya Embedded Language is a scripting language used in Maya.

Visible Human (VH): The Visible Human Male and Visible Human Project datasets are provided by the National Library of Medicine.

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